

TOURISM POWER OF UZBEKISTAN

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7176286>

Ne'matullayeva Nodirabegim Nodirovna

O'zbekiston davlat jahon tillari talabasi

Ilmiy rahbar **Baxtiyarov Muxtorjon Yakubovich**

Abstract: *Despite the fact that our country has a place in the world tourism market, the level of creating favorable conditions for tourists, improving services, increasing the attractiveness of tourist monuments and increasing advertising is very low. So it is arguable that intoxicants of choice runs the taste in diets.*

Keywords: *Ichan Qala, Khiva, Samarkand, Tashkent, Amir Temur, Rome, Babylon, Tillaqori, Termiz, Bukhara, Termez, Karakalpakstan, Kalon Minaret, Registan, Gori Amir, Bibi Khanum, Shahi Zinda.*

Аннотация: *Несмотря на то, что наша страна занимает место на мировом туристическом рынке, уровень создания благоприятных условий для туристов, улучшения услуг, повышения привлекательности туристических памятников и увеличения рекламы очень низок. Таким образом, можно утверждать, что предпочтение отдается предпочтительным наркотикам в диетах.*

Ключевые слова: *Ичан-Кала, Хива, Самарканд, Ташкент, Амир Темур, Рим, Вавилон, Тилакори, Термез, Бухара, Термез, Каракалпакстан, минарет Калон, Регистан, Гори Эмир, Биби Ханум, Шахи Зинда.*

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan attracts the attention of the whole world with its many historical and architectural monuments, unique climate and rapid development. For centuries, Uzbekistan has been on the Great Silk Road for trade, merchants and travelers, geographers and missionaries, invaders and conquerors. At the same time, Uzbekistan is becoming one of the most attractive tourist destinations for those who are interested in culture, history, traditions and exotic countries. Uzbekistan is proud of its architectural monuments that have survived to the present day. The Ichan Qala complex in Khiva, the historical centers in Bukhara, the cities of Shakhrisabz and Samarkand are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List. The unique monuments and architectural structures of these cities reflect the past and play a major role in the history of the country.

REFERENCES AND METHODOLOGY

In the course of the analysis of this article, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev's Law on Physical Culture and Sports has been identified as a methodological source. Logical, historical, coherent and objective methods of scientific knowledge were widely used in the research process. The tourism industry in Uzbekistan has been objectively revealed.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS Tashkent

Tashkent is the capital of Uzbekistan and one of the largest cities in Central Asia. As in the distant past, Tashkent is now a crossroads of international transport routes with the help of our Uzbek airlines and international airlines. Tashkent is one of the oldest cities in the world. In 2009, it celebrated its 2,200th anniversary. At the same time, Tashkent is a modern production center, where more than 500 companies offer a variety of products; from airplanes to tractors, from televisions to textiles and footwear. Tashkent is rapidly becoming a modern international metropolis with a combination of historical monuments and modern skyscrapers. Today, there are about a hundred museums in Uzbekistan, half of which are located in the capital. Each of them reflects the rich cultural heritage of the Uzbek people. In the center of the capital is the State Museum of the History of the Timurids, whose huge blue dome is reminiscent of the ancient dome of Samarkand. His exhibits testify to the formation of medieval forms of statehood in the territory of Uzbekistan and reflect the development of science, culture and art during the reign of Amir Temur.

Samarkand

For centuries, the cities of Uzbekistan have played an important role in the life of the Great Silk Road and the ancient transcontinental highway. Only Samarkand is called the "heart of the Great Silk Road." In ancient times, Samarkand was described as the "Pearl of Islamic Architecture", "Mirror of the World". Samarkand, which is as ancient as Rome, Athens and Babylon, celebrated its 2750th anniversary. Samarkand reached its peak when Genghis Khan was chosen as the capital of the great Movarounnahr state during the reign of Amir Temur, the ruler of Central Asia. During this time, extensive urban planning work was carried out. The great ruler Amir Temur gathered in Samarkand the most skilled craftsmen and masters of his time, and their works have lived on for centuries. Ulugbek, the grandson of Amir Temur, continued these traditions. Today the monuments in Samarkand are beautiful and huge. In this city one can feel the breath of ancient history preserved in ancient ruins, madrasas, mausoleums and minarets. The legendary Registan Square is a unique architectural monument of Central Asia. In

ancient times, this area was the commercial and social center of Samarkand. Three great buildings of several centuries, Ulugbek, Sherdor and Tillaqori madrasas, were erected here. Gori Amir

Mausoleum is another gem of ancient Samarkand. The tombs of the great ruler Amir Temur and his two grandchildren, including the great scientist and thinker of the East Mirzo Ulugbek are located there. The mausoleum of Gori Amir, which resembles a bud with densely arranged leaves of blue tulips, is a very popular place for tourists. Registan Square, Gori Amir, Bibi Khanum, Shahi Zinda mausoleums, Ulugbek Observatory, as well as a number of monuments continue to fascinate visitors to the city.

Bukhara

From ancient times Bukhara has been the densely populated center of the oasis. He is 2,500 years old. Bukhara remains one of the most popular tourist destinations, with a comfortable environment and more than 140 ancient architectural monuments. The mausoleum of Ismail Somoni, the huge fortress and the stronghold of the ruler of Bukhara, the Ark, the Kalon Minaret, many mosques and madrasas, caravanserais, baths and other monuments are like the unique pearls of holy Bukhara. lib remains.

Khiva

Khiva is a city that has been completely preserved since the time of the Great Silk Road. It is called the "open-air museum." The Ichan Qala complex, home to many architectural monuments in the city center, dates from the late 18th century to the first half of the 19th century. Because it is located at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road and the caravan route passes through it, Ichan Qala was built with four gates facing the four corners of the world. The height of the castle wall gives the city a charming look, just like in real oriental fairy tales. The towers are said to reach the sky, and the tallest tower in Uzbekistan is Islamkhoja. The gleaming blue domes of mausoleums and mosques stand on the flat roofs of houses. Several of the khan's palaces have survived in Khiva, the most famous of which is the huge Tashhovli Palace, where the khan's ceremonies, rest and khan's harems are located. The exterior and walls are covered with mosaic decorative stones. It takes less than a day to get to know the splendor of the city, explore its narrow streets and feel the original taste of the "open-air museum".

Termez

The multifaceted history of Uzbekistan undoubtedly reflects its geographical location. Termez is the southernmost city in the country. Termez was founded on a caravan route on the right bank of the Amu Darya and has served as its main port for 2,500 years. At the beginning of the century, Termez was the main center of

Buddhism in Central Asia. The stone-carved Buddhist monastery in Qoratepa, the Buddhist temple in Fayoztepa, and the remains of many limestone Buddhist statues are popular destinations for tourists and Buddhists. Termez is famous not only for its Buddhist monuments. There are also a number of interesting historical monuments dating back to the early Middle Ages. Among them are the tomb of Hakim at-Termizi, the ensemble of Sultan Saodat (X-XVII centuries) and the legendary Kyrgyz fortress (IX century).

Karakalpakstan

Today, Karakalpakstan is a living link between the present and the ancient past. This place is ready to share its legends and secrets with interesting and unique places, unexpected discoveries and discoveries. The Kyrgyz, Ayozkala, Jonboskala, Ishan kala mausoleums, unique Tuprakkala and other historical and memorial monuments in Karakalpakstan arouse scientific and cultural interest, attract local and foreign tourists. . The traditions and customs of the Uzbek people living at the crossroads of the Great Silk Road have been formed over the centuries as a result of the customs of Zoroastrians, Sogdians, Bactrians and nomadic tribes, as well as Islamic traditions. During the trip around Uzbekistan, tourists can not only see the architectural monuments, but also take part in the celebration of national holidays. Each itinerary includes visits to local homes for tourists to see the local lifestyle, taste national dishes and watch folklore shows. The Uzbek national cuisine is especially noteworthy for its diversity. The dishes reflect the lifestyle and culture of the Uzbek people, based on the rich experience of their ancestors. No subtle taboo can be indifferent to the Uzbek hospitality filled with the smell of spices. Traditional notions of Eastern markets; Abundance, pleasantness, and noise can be clearly seen in the markets of Uzbekistan. A good market should be full of products, colorful, loud and shouting, bargaining. Anyone passing by a row of fruits and vegetables will be amazed by the abundance and variety. Oriental markets are especially striking in summer and autumn. The bustle of the market begins early in the morning and ends late. The invitations of customers by traders, the noise of cars, the sound of national music, the smell of spices and the smell of roast meat, the colorful fruits and vegetables on the shelves

create a unique charm of the eastern market. Old caravanserais have been replaced by modern comfortable hotels. Hotels located in tourist areas can meet the needs of any guest. The only "difficulty" may be in choosing a design or comfort that suits your taste. For those who like European style, there are hotels with modern interiors, and for those who want a pure oriental atmosphere, there are hotels with their own patterned doors, from colorful carpets to oriental porches. You can use first-class hotels in big cities such as Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Urgench. Today, more than 350 hotels in Uzbekistan receive tourists and provide services in accordance with international standards. Uzbekistan now has a developed transport infrastructure. It doesn't take you a month to get there, as it did during the Great Silk Road. Getting to big cities across Uzbekistan by air is quick and easy. Tourists use a car or bus, which is convenient and fast to enjoy the beautiful scenery of the country. Uzbekistan is famous not only for its historical and legendary architecture, but also for its active tourist destinations. The geographical location of our country allows us to combine modern convenience and wildlife. Any natural landscapes on the territory of Uzbekistan; mountains, valleys, deserts, rivers and lakes. The unique nature of Uzbekistan allows you to walk along the Western Tyanshan Mountains and experience the beauty of the mountain. Many climbers and skiers seek extreme sensations in the 3,309-meter-high Chimgan Mountains. Horseback riding is fun for people of all ages and temperaments. It is possible to practice all year round in unique climatic conditions. One of the most popular areas for horseback riding is the Ugam-Chatkal National Park, which is famous for its flora and fauna. The beautiful valley from Tashkent, located at an altitude of 1,600 meters above sea level, at the foot of the Chimgan Mountains, can be reached on horseback by 90 kilometers to the Chimgan Camp. Here you can ride horses of the local breed Karabair, as well as Akhal-Teke. The purity of the mountain air, filled with the scent of various flowers and plants, the squeak of a saddle, the uniform tapping of a horse's hooves, and an emotional open-air breakfast leave a lasting impression. If you want to feel the movement of the Great Silk Road in the distant past, we invite you to take a trip through the Red Sand Desert. Sand dunes, the scorching heat of the sun, saxophones everywhere and the sound of camel bells, and just endless sands In early spring, the life-giving rains cover the desert with a carpet of red tulips and green grass, but this beauty lasts only a short time. Tourists leave their comfortable cars, ride camels and start their exotic journeys. It leaves an unforgettable impression. Imagine what could be nicer than a blood-red dawn, sparkling sand dunes, grassy nights, exotic national dishes, folklore performances, and the heat ?! Somewhat warm weather, complete lack of wind,

300 days of sunshine, the availability of ski-friendly amenities, slalom, cross-country skiing and fast-flying types make skiing a winter vacation in the West. There are very convenient facilities in Tyanshan.

In recent years, the Chimgan-Chorvok-Beldirsoy resort has become one of the most popular destinations for fans of heli-skiing and free riding, a new but fastgrowing sport. Therefore, the snow-capped slopes of the Chimgan Mountains, which are 1600-2400 m above sea level from October to May, are suitable for sports fans in accordance with international skiing standards. For many heli-skiing fans, skiing begins at 4,000 m above sea level and ends in the valley. It is possible to fly there 6 times a day in the snow, which has not yet been skied. Fans rafting on local fastflowing rivers also refer to Uzbekistan as the "Switzerland of Asia." Rafting along the Chatkal River is a favorite pastime of sports fans. They are interested in the fact that the route is multi-day, level 5 in terms of difficulty, as well as the landscape, the number of obstacles. There will be no less than 50 obstacles in this direction. The most difficult of them are waterfalls, fast-flowing slopes, shallow rocks, streams, rocky streams. Favorable climate, fresh air, beautiful scenery and natural landscape. The Lake Tashkent Golf Club consists of 18 108-hectare pits, evergreen lawns, many trees and cliffs, lakes and waterfalls. These make the game more interesting by creating natural barriers. The beautiful lake and the surrounding area give each of the 18 pits a special feature. There are also training grounds, tennis courts, swimming pools and saunas. Although the tourism sector in Uzbekistan is relatively new, it has outperformed many other sectors. Our country has a great potential for the development of international tourism. Twenty years ago, no one knew Uzbekistan as a promising tourist destination. After gaining independence, the state has developed new principles in the field of tourism. On July 27, 1992, the National Company "Uzbektourism" was established by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main task of Uzbektourism is to implement state policy in the field of tourism and create a national model of tourism development. In addition, the national company coordinates the activities of all tourism organizations in the country, encourages the development of all areas of tourism, deals with human resources, attracts investment in the formation of material and technical base and the development of infrastructure. Since 1993, our country has been a member of the International Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Since 2004, the UNWTO Office for Tourism Coordination on the Transcontinental Highway has been operating in Samarkand, the "heart" of the Great Silk Road.

CONCLUSION

The government is working hard to modernize the tourism sector, improve the transport and hotel infrastructure in the country, as well as improve the regulatory framework for tourism. In order to promote tourism products abroad, the marketing project "Mega-info-tour" - dating trips is being implemented for foreign travel companies and the media. Such trips play an important role in expanding the tourist season, optimizing the flow of tourists to our country, as well as showing that each season in Uzbekistan is unique for tourists. In addition, the UNWTO-led International Silk Road Tourism Fair in Tashkent plays an important role in supporting the tourism potential of Uzbekistan. The main purpose of the fair is to unite Uzbek and foreign experts in the field of tourism, to further expand professional cooperation between them. Today, the international fair is one of the largest in Central Asia. In conclusion, Uzbekistan, with its legendary past, historical and engineering heritage of the Silk Road, magnificent landscapes, local handicrafts passed down from generation to generation, the hospitality and human values of the people. It attracts people from all over Uzbekistan, which amazes and fascinates tourists.

REFERENCES:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Culture and Sports". Tashkent, 1992.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education". Tashkent 1997
3. R.A. Abdumalikov, T. Kholdorov "Tourism". Tashkent "Teacher" 1988
4. M.A. Verba, SM. Golisin, V.M. Kulikov, Ye.G. Ryabov "Tourism at school" Tashkent "Teacher" 1990.
5. Khalimovna, T. S. (2021). THE PROBLEMS OF SOCIAL AND ETHNIC CONFLICTS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(4), 1532-1536.
6. Mamasaliev, M. M. (2020). INCREASING THE EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES OF SOCIAL INSTITUTIONS IN THE PROCESS OF INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT. In *ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 204-206).
7. Мамасалиев, М. М., & Нематов, Д. С. (2019). ВОПРОСЫ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ВЫСШЕМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (4-4), 70-72.

8. Буриев, И. И., & Мамасалиев, М. М. (2020). ПАТРИОТИЧЕСКОЕ ВОСПИТАНИЕ МОЛОДОГО ПОКОЛЕНИЯ. *Вестник науки и образования*, (22-2 (100)).
9. Очиллова, Н. Р., & Мамасалиев, М. М. (2021). ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКИ ВОСТОЧНОЙ И ЗАПАДНОЙ ЦИВИЛИЗАЦИИ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ГЛОБАЛИЗАЦИИ. *Проблемы науки*, 43.
10. Mamasaliev, M. M. (2020). MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MODERN CIVILIZATION ON THE SPIRITUAL IMAGE OF THE INDIVIDUAL. *Вестник науки*, 3(11), 5-8.
11. Allanazarov, M. K., & Mamasaliev, M. M. (2020). ANALYSIS OF COMPREHENSION METHODS IN THE GNOSEOLOGY OF ALLAME TABATABAI. In *ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 106-109).
12. Курбонова, М. Б., & Мамасалиев, М. М. (2020). СТРУКТУРА СОЦИАЛЬНОГО СТАТУСА МОЛОДЕЖНОГО СООБЩЕСТВА. In *ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ РАЗВИТИЕ: ПОТЕНЦИАЛ НАУКИ И СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 210-213).